

INTEGRATING SUSTAINABILITY AND HEALTH IN
BUILDINGS THROUGH RENEWABLE MATERIALS

INNORENEW CoE INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE
2020

INNORENEW CoE

Livade 6, 6310 Izola, Slovenia

IRIC2020 SCIENTIFIC COMMITTEE

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WELCOME

As we open the second InnoRenew CoE International Conference, it's hard not to think of all that has changed in the year and a half that has passed since our debut conference.

Although the pandemic has dramatically changed our day-to-day lives, it has not changed society's need to address the rapidly changing climate, reconsider our economic priorities, and refocus our attention on important social issues. Buildings remain part of the solution to many problems, and I think it is becoming clear that we need to consider much more about buildings than the basics of shelter.

As the pandemic kept us indoors, many of us may have realised that our indoor environment plays an even more important role in our well-being and happiness than we previously acknowledged. Likewise, we may have considered more carefully how buildings affect the well-being of those who live in different circumstances. Access to safe, comfortable, and healthy living and working spaces is (and should be) a priority in a just society.

Another major change that will affect our work in the years to come is the introduction of the European Green Deal, which will be a major driver of sustainable development in Europe. The European Green Deal prioritises investment and innovation in building renovation solutions for energy performance and attempts to ensure these solutions reach all members of society. The European Green Deal recognizes the need to establish high-performance housing for all and will support renovation in social housing, schools, and other facilities that are often left behind. This is a step in the right direction for inclusive, high-performing buildings.

I rarely find proclamations of success convincing when it comes to sustainability – especially about buildings. We must continue to drive change through research, development, and innovation to make our built environment a beacon of sustainable development. We cannot be satisfied with the environmental performance of our products or buildings; we cannot allow people to be excluded from our advancements; and we cannot forget that buildings impact the well-being and happiness of their occupants.

At this year's InnoRenew CoE International Conference, we wanted to showcase how renewable materials play an integral role in sustainable construction by highlighting environmental performance, safety, and health as well as the economic, digital, and social links that bind us to the materials in the built environment. Conference presenters will discuss advances in design, material development, health research, retrofitting, environmental assessment, and many other topics that increase the efficiency and performance of the building and renewable materials sectors.

Carlo Battisti, President of Living Future Europe, will weave together these complementary threads in his keynote address, "Healthy, living transparent. The quiet revolution of materials". He works to push for change and supports researchers, architects, engineers, and other construction professionals to achieve it. His efforts have expanded knowledge and acceptance of restorative sustainability and regenerative design within Europe's construction community. We are excited and grateful for his participation in our conference.

Together, the contributions paint a hopeful picture. But we must continue to push the science forward, embed these innovations in normal construction practices, and ensure inclusion of all who can benefit from our hard work.

While I wish these matters could have been discussed in person in Izola, we must embrace new options for discourse on these topics. I hope the conference inspires you to reach out to one another and continue sharing, collaborating, and building communities that embrace the challenge of creating a sustainable and just built environment. You may also consider our new open access and peer-reviewed journal, *Interdisciplinary Perspectives on the Built Environment*, as a place to share the insights your work provides.

Thank you,

Dr Michael Burnard
Deputy Director, InnoRenew CoE
Assist. Prof., University of Primorska

SCHEDULE AT A GLANCE

MORNING

WELCOME
9:00–9:05

KEYNOTE
9:05–9:35

FLASH TALKS
9:35–10:35

COFFEE BREAK
10:35–11:00

**HUMAN HEALTH IN THE
BUILT ENVIRONMENT**
11:00–12:30

LUNCH
12:30–14:00

AFTERNOON

COMPLEMENTARY TOPICS
14:00–15:30

COFFEE BREAK
15:30–15:55

**SUSTAINABLE CONSTRUCTION
WITH RENEWABLE MATERIALS**
15:55–17:25

CLOSING
17:25–17:30

KEYNOTE ADDRESS

CARLO BATTISTI
PRESIDENT, LIVING FUTURE EUROPE

*Healthy, living, transparent.
The quiet revolution of materials.*

Carlo Battisti has a degree in civil engineering from the Politecnico of Milan, nearly twenty years of experience in construction companies and a master's in management and organizational development from MIP International Business School. His certifications include Certified Project Manager IPMA®; LEED®, Living Future and WELL Accredited Professional; GBC Home AP, GBC Historic Building AP; USGBC® and WELL Faculty™.

Since 2009, he has been working with IDM South Tyrol (Italy) as an innovation manager in the Business Development department, Construction. From 2010 to 2011, he worked with the Energy and Environment Cluster of Trentino as manager of the business unit for sustainable products. From 2015 to 2016, he was the co-owner of a startup focused on LEED consulting. In 2015, he co-founded the Living Future Italy Collaborative.

Since 2017, he has been working with Eurac Research as Chair and Project Manager of COST Action 16114 RESTORE (REthinking Sustainability TOwards a Regenerative Economy). The RESTORE COST Action (2017–2021) will affect a paradigm shift towards restorative sustainability for new and existing buildings and space design across Europe through the collaboration of 160+ researchers from 40 European countries.

Since 2018, he is European Executive Director for the International Living Future Institute and current President of Living Future Europe. The Institute's mission will hasten the change and provide needed direction towards a regenerative design transition in Europe. It is actively pursuing European market alignment and adaptations of the Living Building Challenge (LBC).

AGENDA

WELCOME | 9:00-9:05

Dr Michael Burnard, InnoRenew CoE

KEYNOTE | 9:05-9:35

Carlo Battisti, Living Future Europe

FLASH TALKS | 9:35-10:35

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*Unable to present

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CLOSING | 17:25-17:30

THANK YOU FOR ATTENDING IRIC2020!

SEE YOU NEXT YEAR

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Complementary Topics

Towards Smart Textiles for Civil Engineering Application

L. Marrot¹, J. Grkman², J. Včelák³

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Integration of sensors or any other diagnostic technology directly into a material or structure is a way to increase the safety level of the construction and provide other features as online diagnostics, predictive maintenance or a functionality of early warning in case of component failure. Many of the available embedded sensor technologies suffer from limited lifetime or necessity to have a battery power or influence the structure integrity. Technologies with lower impact on the structure, as integration of Fiber Bragg Gratings sensors, require expensive sensitive equipment to evaluate signals. Application of sensitive coatings on the textiles for reinforcement purpose is a novel and innovative approach. Using textile for the reinforcement of concrete and composites allows subtle and still high-performance structures to be built. The textile itself can be used as substrate for layers providing sensing functionality to measure moisture, strain, load or to detect cracks in the material. The main advantage is the direct contact of these additional layers with the measured material, in situ measurement, as well as protection of the sensitive textile against ambient environmental conditions.

This paper will introduce flax textile reinforcement as sustainable alternative to synthetic reinforcement material, coated with carbon-filled epoxy resin. The carbon provides conductivity properties to the textile. Graphite and bio-carbon will be studied in this work. A detailed study of textile conductivity properties with respect to the carbon concentration in epoxy will be presented in the full paper. The promising results obtained with textile coated by epoxy filled with graphite shows suitable conductivity levels for embedded strain/load measurement in civil engineering. The results of epoxy-graphite and epoxy bio-carbon mixtures will be shown together with the coated textile conductivity study. The potential for applications in moisture detection in timber constructions such as CLT or GLT will be discussed in the full paper as well.

Keywords: smart textile, embedded sensing, renewable materials

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